

¿SABES DAR ÓRDENES, CONSEJOS, PROHIBIR O ADVERTIR EN INGLÉS?. ¿CÓMO EXPRESAMOS LA OBLIGACIÓN EN INGLÉS?

PRIMERA LENGUA EXTRANJERA: INGLÉS 4º ESO

PRESENTACIÓN

En este proyecto vamos a aprender a dar órdenes en inglés, ofrecer consejos, formular prohibiciones y expresar advertencias por medio de distintas formas lingüísticas como los verbos modales y los imperativos, así como a entender estas funciones comunicativas en situaciones de la vida cotidiana relacionadas con los medios de transporte y los viajes. Además, estableceremos comparaciones con las formas lingüísticas que empleamos en lengua castellana o en la lengua de la comunidad autónoma en contextos similares, estableciendo semejanzas y diferencias con las que se usan en inglés. El objetivo final es que realicéis un video de TikTok en grupos en el que escenifiquéis diálogos relacionados con los medios de transporte y los viajes en los cuales utilicéis e interpretéis adecuadamente los distintos elementos lingüísticos estudiados, así como las funciones comunicativas descritas para expresar obligación en inglés, y que hagáis una breve explicación de los mismos, siguiendo una pequeña guía ofrecida por el profesor o la profesora.

Let's start!

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DESARROLLO DE LA SECUENCIA DIDÁCTICA

PHASE 1

Session 1 & 2

Activity 1 (warm up)

After watching the following video in YouTube, answer the following questions in your own language.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tw9A3YYMR58>

- What does the expression “mind the gap” mean? Please, look it up in an online dictionary.
- What is the speaker’s intention by saying this expression?
 - ✓ Is he commanding listeners to mind the gap?
 - ✓ Is he advising listeners to mind the gap?
 - ✓ Is he prohibiting listeners to mind the gap?

- ✓ Is he warning listeners to mind the gap?
- Who are the listeners?
- Where are they?
- Why should listeners mind the gap?
- (Optional) You can read the story behind the “mind the gap” voice at <https://twitter.com/garius/status/1204795961731629058> . Make a summary and bring it to class.

Activity 2 (in pairs)

Look at the examples below. Indicate who the speaker is and the listener(s). Then circle the word that expresses what the speaker is doing.

SITUATION 1

Who is the speaker?

Who is/are the listener(s)?

What is the speaker doing?

He is **COMMANDING** (dar una orden) the young man to take the 12:00pm bus.

He is **ADVISING** (aconsejar) the young man to take the 12:00pm bus.

Imagen de Adobe Stock File # [457026623](#)

SITUATION 2

Who is the speaker?

Who is/are the listener(s)?

What is the speaker doing? Can you describe her body language?

She is **COMMANDING** (dar una orden) her friend to buy a bigger suitcase.

She is **ADVISING** (aconsejar) her friend to buy a bigger suitcase.

Imagen de Adobe Stock File # [318458853](#)

SITUATION 3

Who is the speaker?

Who is/are the listener(s)?

What is the speaker doing?

The speaker is **COMMANDING** (dar una orden) people not to disturb.

The speaker is **ADVISING** (aconsejar) people not to disturb.

Imagen de Todd Pearson 200020744-001

SITUATION 4

Who is the speaker?

Who is/are the listener(s)?

What is the speaker doing?

The speaker is **COMMANDING** (dar una orden) her boyfriend to turn right.

The speaker is **ADVISING** (aconsejar) her boyfriend to turn right.

Imagen de [jacoblund](#) 514567290

Activity 3 (in pairs)

Complete the table by looking at the examples in Activity 2.

COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	CONTEXTS	LANGUAGE FORMS	
		IN ENGLISH	IN SPANISH
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> COMMAND <input type="checkbox"/> ADVISE	Situation: In the bus, giving directions Speaker: Bus driver Listener(s): A passenger or young man	Have to (<i>You have to take the 12:00pm bus</i>)	Tiene que coger el autobús de las 12:00pm.
<input type="checkbox"/> COMMAND <input type="checkbox"/> ADVISE	Situation: Speaker: Listener(s):		

<input type="checkbox"/> COMMAND <input type="checkbox"/> ADVISE	Situation: Speaker: Listener(s):		
<input type="checkbox"/> COMMANDING <input type="checkbox"/> ADVISING	Situation: Speaker: Listener(s):		

Activity 4 (in pairs)

Look at the examples below. Indicate who the speaker is and the listener(s). Then circle the word that expresses what the speaker is doing.

Imagen de <https://metro.co.uk/2021/09/28/women-followed-lockdown-rules-more-closely-than-men-study-shows-15330411/>

SITUATION 5

Who is the speaker?

Who is/are the listener(s)?

What is the speaker doing?

The speaker is **PROHIBITING** (prohibir) people to keep their distance.

The speaker is **WARNING** (advertir) people to keep their distance.

SITUATION 6

Who is the speaker?

Who is/are the listener(s)?

What is the speaker doing?

She is **PROHIBITING** (prohibir) her father to smoke.

She is **WARNING** (advertir) her father not to smoke.

Imagen de [Zabavna](#) en Adobe Stock 147837269

Imagen de shutterstock por Rosemarie Mosteller 1950144733

SITUATION 7

Who is the speaker?

Who is/are the listener(s)?

What is the speaker doing?

The speaker is **PROHIBITING** (prohibir) people to cross tracks.

The speaker is **WARNING** (advertir) people not to cross tracks.

SITUATION 8

Who is the speaker?

Who is the listener?

What is the speaker doing?

The speaker is **PROHIBITING** (prohibir) the man to park there.

The speaker is **WARNING** (advertir) the man not to park there.

Imagen de <https://brettpodolsky.com/search-and-seizure/illegal-search-and-seizure-in-texas>

ACTIVITY 5 (in pairs)

Complete the table by looking at the examples in Activity 4.

COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	CONTEXTS	LANGUAGE FORMS	
		IN ENGLISH	IN SPANISH
<input type="checkbox"/> PROHIBIT <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WARN	Situation: At the train station Speaker: The authority, the staff at the train station Listener(s): Passengers	Imperative form (<i>Keep your distance</i>)	Mantenga o mantengan la distancia.
<input type="checkbox"/> PROHIBIT <input type="checkbox"/> WARN	Situation: Speaker: Listener(s):		
<input type="checkbox"/> PROHIBIT <input type="checkbox"/> WARN	Situation: Speaker: Listener(s):		

<input type="checkbox"/> PROHIBIT <input type="checkbox"/> WARN	Situation: Speaker: Listener(s):		
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PHASE 2

Sessions 3, 4 & 5

In the previous activities, we have seen how speakers command, advise, prohibit, and warn listeners in English using different linguistic forms across situations. With these activities in mind, please do the activities below.

Activity 6 (in pairs)

PART A. Complete the conversations by choosing the correct linguistic form(s). Then answer the questions below.

Imagen de [lorenzoantonucci](https://www.istockphoto.com/lorenzoantonucci) en istockphoto.com 531224069

CONVERSATION 1

Michael: I _____

(MUST/HAVE TO) get up early tomorrow to catch a flight.

Will: Yes, definitely.

Imagen de <https://www.psychologieintheater.nl/coronadip/>

CONVERSATION 2

We _____ **(MUST/HAVE TO)** wear medical masks in the metro.

CONVERSATION 3

Sue on the phone: So at what time will you be home?

Tom: I _____ **(MUST/HAVE TO)** be back home before midnight according to COVID regulations.

Imagen de [Maridav](https://www.istockphoto.com/Maridav) en istockphoto.com 1171649240

- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **MUST/HAVE TO** en la conversación 1? ¿Es posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.
- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **MUST/HAVE TO** en la conversación 2? ¿Es posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.
- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **MUST/HAVE TO** en la conversación 3? ¿Es posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.

PART B. Now read the explanations in the following table, and complete. Then offer 1 more example.

How do we express obligation in English?				
LANGUAGE FORMS		MEANING	COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	SITUATIONS
We use HAVE TO (In Spanish)	In affirmative form:	to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) that you cannot avoid	in order to _____ someone or yourself to do something	Situations: Regulations and norms; daily conversations in which the speaker is an authority figure or conversations between equals
EXAMPLES				
<p>Example 1: (Mother to son): You <i>have to</i> pick up your sister from school at 5:00 pm. (The speaker is COMMANDING her son to pick up his sister).</p> <p>Example 2:</p> <hr/>				

Activity 7 (in pairs)

PART A. Complete the signs and the conversation by choosing the correct linguistic form(s). Then answer the questions below.

SITUATION 4

Imagen de www.pinterest.es
276478864602249155

Please _____
(TURN OFF/MUST TURN OFF)
your mobile phones.

SITUATION 5

Imagen de de Caia Image / SCIENCE PHOTO
LIBRARY 897514

Air stewardess: Sir,
_____ **(FASTEN/YOU
MUST FASTEN)** your seat belt, please. We
are already taking off.

SITUATION 6

I _____
(HAVE TO/MUST) respect the
other passengers, and lower the
volume.

Imagen de <https://www.teamcassracing.top/ProductDetail.aspx?iid=201250308&pr=37.88>

- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **IMPERATIVO/MUST** en la situación 4? ¿Es posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.
- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **IMPERATIVO/MUST** en la situación 5? ¿Es posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.
- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **HAVE TO/MUST** en la situación 6? ¿Es

posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.

PART B. Now read the explanations in the following tables, and complete them by offering 1 more example.

How do we express obligation in English?					
LANGUAGE FORMS		MEANING	COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	SITUATIONS	
We use IMPERATIVE (In Spanish) _____	In affirmative form (e.g., to keep): _____ in negative form (e.g., to keep): _____	to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) that you cannot avoid	in order to _____ someone to do something	Situations: Signs and daily conversations in which the speaker is an authority figure	
EXAMPLES					
<p>Example 1: (Sign on the wall of a hospital): Please <i>keep</i> quiet. (The sign is COMMANDING people to keep quiet)</p> <p>Example 2: _____</p>					

How do we express obligation in English?					
LANGUAGE FORMS		MEANING	COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	SITUATIONS	
We use MUST (In Spanish) _____	In affirmative form: _____ _____	to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) that you can avoid.	in order to _____ someone to do something that s/he may not do; in order to _____ someone or yourself on something	Situations: Signs, regulations and norms, and daily conversations in which the speaker is an authority figure or between equals	
EXAMPLES					

Example 1:

(Sign on the wall of a toilette): You *must* wash your hands often (The sign is **COMMANDING** people to wash their hands often).

Example 2:

I *must* study harder, if I want to pass this course (The speaker is **ADVISING** himself to study harder).

Example 3:

Activity 8 (in pairs)

PART A. Complete the conversations by choosing the correct linguistic form(s). Then answer the questions below.

Imagen de Frame Stock Footage en shutterstock.com video/clip-1008584770

CONVERSATION 7

Customs officer: Sorry, we _____ (**MUSTN'T/CAN'T**) let you in the flight. Your passport has expired.

Jim: I thought it was alright.

CONVERSATION 9

Dad: You _____

(**MUSTN'T/SHOULDN'T**) leave your bags far from you at the bus station.

Tim: Ok dad.

Imagen de [monkeybusinessimages](https://www.monkeybusinessimages.com) en istockphoto 826211942

CONVERSATION 8

Nina: When do you have your exam?

John: Tomorrow

Nina: You _____ (**MUST/SHOULD**) rest tonight, if you want to do well.

Imagen de <https://education.nsw.gov.au/>

- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **MUSTN'T/CAN'T** en la conversación 7? ¿Es

posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.

- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **MUST/SHOULD** en la conversación **8**? ¿Es posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.
- ¿Por qué has elegido la forma **MUSTN'T/SHOULDN'T** en la conversación **9**? ¿Es posible escoger ambas? Tanto en caso afirmativo como negativo, explica por qué.

PART B. Now read the explanations in the following tables, and complete them by offering 1 more example.

How do we express obligation in English?				
LANGUAGE FORMS		MEANING	COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	SITUATIONS
We use CANNOT/CAN'T (In Spanish)	In negative form:	to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) that you cannot avoid.	in order to _____ someone to do something.	Situations: Regulations and norms, and daily conversations in which the speaker is an authority figure
EXAMPLES				
<p>Example 1: (Nurse to patient smoking in the waiting room): You <i>can't</i> smoke indoors, madam. (The speaker is PROHIBITING the woman to smoke).</p> <p>Example 2: _____</p>				

How do we express obligation in English?				
LANGUAGE FORMS		MEANING	COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	SITUATIONS
We use MUST NOT/ MUSTN'T/ (In Spanish)	In negative form:	to express (strong, medium, weak obligation) that you can avoid.	In order to someone about something.	Situations: Signs, regulations and norms, and daily conversations in which the speaker is an authority figure or between equals
EXAMPLES				
<p>Example 1: (Granny to grand-daughter): You <i>must not/mustn't</i> cross the street without looking first if a car is coming. (The speaker is WARNING her grand-daughter to look before crossing).</p> <p>Example 3:</p>				

How do we express obligation in English?				
LANGUAGE FORMS		MEANING	COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	SITUATIONS
We use SHOULD (In Spanish)	In affirmative form: in negative form:	to express (strong, medium, weak obligation) that you can avoid	In order to someone or yourself on something.	Situations: Daily conversations in which the speaker is an authority figure or between equals
EXAMPLES				
<p>Example 1: (Friend to another friend): I <i>should</i> do some exercise, if I want to lose weight. (The speaker is ADVISING herself to do some exercise).</p> <p>Example 2:</p>				

Activity 9 (in pairs)

Answer the following questions in your own language and complete the table below.

- ¿En qué situaciones das o recibes una orden?, ¿y un consejo?
- ¿A quién diriges la orden?, ¿y el consejo?
- ¿Quién o qué te la da la orden?, ¿y el consejo?
- ¿Para qué normalmente das o te dan una orden?, ¿y un consejo?
- ¿En qué lenguas o contextos (p.ej. video tutoriales, videojuegos, etc.) has observado, recibido o formulado una orden?, ¿y un consejo?
- ¿Recuerdas cómo se expresa dicha orden? En caso afirmativo, indica la forma o formas lingüísticas.
- ¿Recuerdas cómo se expresa el consejo? En caso afirmativo, indica la forma o formas lingüísticas.

	DAR/RECIBIR UNA ORDEN (COMMAND)	DAR/RECIBIR UN CONSEJO (ADVISE)
Situaciones (Situations)		
¿Quién? (Who?)		
¿Para qué? (What for?)		
Lenguas (Languages)		
Formas lingüísticas (Language forms)		

Activity 10 (in pairs)

Answer the following questions in your own language and complete the table below.

- ¿En qué situaciones prohíbes, te prohíben algo, adviertes o te advierten de algo?
- ¿A quién diriges la prohibición?, ¿y la advertencia?
- ¿Quién o qué te prohíbe algo o te advierte de algo?
- ¿Para qué normalmente prohíbes, te prohíben algo, adviertes o te advierten de algo?
- ¿En qué lenguas o contextos has observado, recibido o formulado una prohibición?, ¿y una advertencia?
- ¿Recuerdas cómo se expresa dicha prohibición? En caso afirmativo, indica la forma o formas lingüísticas.
- ¿Recuerdas cómo se expresa dicha advertencia? En caso afirmativo, indica la forma o formas lingüísticas.

	PROHIBIR/RECIBIR UNA PROHIBICIÓN (PROHIBIT)	ADVERTIR/RECIBIR UNA ADVERTENCIA (WARN)
Situaciones (Situations)		
¿Quién? (Who?)		
¿Para qué? (What for?)		
Lenguas (Languages)		
Formas lingüísticas (Language forms)		

Wrapping up

PHASE 3

Sessions 6 & 7

Activity 11

PART A (individual). Below you can find the synopsis of the film *Passengers* (Pasajeros). Read it carefully and then move to Part b of this activity.

SYNOPSIS

A *spaceship* is on a 120-year *voyage* to *colonise* a new planet. The passengers on board will be in *hibernation* for nearly all the *journey*. However, after only 30 years, one of the passengers, Jim Preston, *wakes up* from his hibernation due to a *malfunction* in the spaceship. He tries to go back to hibernation, but it is impossible. Out of loneliness and despair, he *de-hibernates* a female passenger, Aurora. Both fall in love, and enjoy the spaceship talking to the robot Arthur. The robot tells Aurora that Jim woke her up, and she is *devastated*, because she will never get to live in the new planet. Finally, Jim discovers how to *re-hibernate* her but Aurora decides to stay with him.

VOCABULARY NOTE

- *Spaceship*: nave espacial.
- *Voyage*: viaje.
- *Colonise*: colonizar.
- *Hibernation*: hibernación.
- *Journey*: trayecto.
- *Wake up*: despertarse.
- *Malfunction*: mal funcionamiento.
- *De-hibernates*: des-hibernar.
- *Devastated*: devastada.
- *Re-hibernate*: re-hibernar.

PART B (in groups). To become familiar with the film, watch the trailer in Spanish at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8JuGv5x152w>. Then write a short dialogue for the vignette of your group with at least three language forms that express obligation (**HAVE TO, IMPERATIVE, MUST, CAN'T, MUSTN'T/MUST NOT, and SHOULD/SHOULDN'T**). Imágenes de Passengers © Columbia Pictures

Context: Jim and Aurora talk about the malfunction in the spaceship...

GROUP 1 - DIALOGUE

Context: Jim decides to go outside into space to try to solve the problem of the spaceship...

GROUP 2 - DIALOGUE

Context: Aurora just discovered that Jim woke her up...

GROUP 3 - DIALOGUE

Context: Aurora saves Jim and decides to stay with him...

GROUP 4 - DIALOGUE

PART B (in groups). Now classify the language forms you used according to the items in the table below.

LANGUAGE FORMS	MEANING (STRONG, MEDIUM, WEAK OBLIGATION)	COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION	FORMAS LINGÜÍSTICAS

Activity 12 (in 4 small groups). Revision

PART A. According to the dialogues in Activity 11, each group has to make a TikTok video in class acting out the dialogue (*remember to bring clothes and objects that may be useful for the scene). Group members should participate equally in the conversation. Here you have an example.

PART B. Now answer the questions in the table in your own language for each language form that you used.

QUESTIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What did you want to express with _____ (language form 1, 2, 3)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Strong obligation? ✓ Medium obligation? ✓ Weak obligation? • Which communicative function did you want to perform with (language form 1, 2, 3)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ To command? ✓ To advise? ✓ To prohibit? ✓ To warn? • Who is the speaker? who are the listeners? Is any of them an authority figure? What is their relationship? • Why did you choose _____ (language form 1, 2, 3) as opposed to other language forms?
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PART C. Bring your group video to class. Conversations and answers to the questions will be discussed.

Wrapping up

We use **HAVE TO** to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) in order to _____ (command, advise, prohibit, warn) listeners in situations in which:

- Regulations and norms are involved
- The speaker is an authority figure

- The speaker and listener are equals

For example: _____

We use **IMPERATIVE** to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) in order to _____ (command, advise, prohibit, warn) listeners in situations in which:

- Regulations and norms are involved
- The speaker is an authority figure
- The speaker and listener are equals

For example: _____

We use **MUST** to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) in order to _____ (command, advise, prohibit, warn) listeners in situations in which:

- Regulations and norms are involved
- The speaker is an authority figure
- The speaker and listener are equals

For example: _____

We use **CANNOT/CAN'T** to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) to prohibit (command, advise, prohibit, warn) something to listeners in situations in which:

- Regulations and norms are involved
- The speaker is an authority figure
- The speaker and listener are equals

For example: _____

We use **MUST NOT/MUSTN'T** to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) in order to _____ (command, advise, prohibit, warn) listeners in situations in which:

- Regulations and norms are involved
- The speaker is an authority figure
- The speaker and listener are equals

For example: _____

We use **SHOULD/SHOULDN'T** to express _____ (strong, medium, weak obligation) in order to _____ (command, advise, prohibit, warn) listeners in situations in which:

- Regulations and norms are involved
- The speaker is an authority figure
- The speaker and listener are equals

For example: _____